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Assembly Twin

D5.1: Cellular neural networks and multicriteria optimization

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Abstract:	This deliverable (D5.1) reports on the development and results of advanced battery health optimization and performance within T5.1 of the project. The work focuses on creating a self-supervised Cellular Neural Network (CeNN) predictor to provide real-time and adaptable battery State of Health (SOH) by leveraging a student-teacher learning framework. Additionally, the deliverable covers T5.2, i.e. the implementation of Multi-Criteria Optimization (MCO) for dynamic, staged Constant Current (CC) charging protocols, which enables optimized balance charging speed, safety, and battery longevity.
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	Furthermore, Long-Term State Forecasting (LTSF) models are developed for predictive maintenance, enabling reliable SOH and capacity fade predictions over extended battery life cycles. The utilization of these models is supported by the DoE/DoS developments under T5.2 and the interoperability constructions integrated from T3.4 and T4.4.
Keywords	ML trained by simulated & characterization data; MCO, DoE, DoS

Author list

Beneficiary	Name	Contact e-mail
ITWM	Peter Klein	peter.klein@itwm.fraunhofer.de
ITWM	Marco Baldan	marco.baldan@itwm.fraunhofer.de
NMBU	Aditya Dey	aditya.dey@nmbu.no
NMBU	Fadi Al Machot	fadi.al.machot@nmbu.no

Reviewer list

Beneficiary	Name	Contact e-mail
HSKL	Johanna Glutting	johanna.glutting@hs-kl.de
NMBU	Maria Bashir	maria.bashir@nmbu.no
AAU	Mohamed El Bahnasawi	mohamed.elbahnasawi@aau.at

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ASP	answer set programming
CC	constant current
CV	constant voltage
CeNN	cellular neural network
DoE	design of experiment
DoS	design of simulation
LIB	Li-ion battery
LTSF	Long-term state forecasting
MCO	multicriteria optimization
RFB	redox flow battery
SoH	state of health

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1. Executive summary

Description of the deliverable content and objectives

Task 5.1 focuses on developing a self-supervised machine-learning predictor for battery health optimization. The core of T5.1 is to design an adaptive, self-supervised Cellular Neural Network (CeNN) predictor which allows for a continuous retraining and improvement. This is integrated with the developments of T5.2, MCO technology, which is one out of several technologies that contribute to the digital twin approach in BatCAT. Design of experiment (DoE) and design of simulation (DoS) have been demonstrated for a combined simulation/experimentation characterization of electrolytes. The main objectives of the tasks related to this deliverable are fulfilled.

2. Progress report (main activities)

2.1 Integration of work streams from work packages different from WP5

Within Work Package 4, Task T4.4 - Metadata standardization, ontologies are being developed to cover all aspects of battery manufacturing, modelling and characterization that will be needed within BatCAT and in particular in Work Package 5. Currently a set of eight modules is being drafted, namely: (a) Higher level; (b) Optimization, decision support, design; (c) Twinning; (d) Data and metadata; (e) Modelling and simulation; (f) Characterization; (g) Manufacturing; (h) Battery (LiB and RFB). Particularly relevant to this deliverable, the module for optimization will cover both logic-based and numerical optimization, which within BatCAT Work Package 5 are tackled by answer set programming (ASP) and multicriteria optimization (MCO), respectively. Currently, for example, it contains concepts such as “*problem*”, “*solution*”, “*constraint*”, which can be “*qualitative*” or “*quantitative*”. In parallel, coverage of BatCAT requirements by existing semantic artifacts is assessed, so that reuse and development are suitably combined. As T4.4 will continue over the next six months, further concepts will be added to cover all requirements. Work Package 5 will pick up the ontology developments from WP 4 as they go, initial integration steps were already undertaken.

2.2 Task T5.1 — Battery health optimization strategies

Within WP5 — Digital Twin Technology, Task 5.1 focuses on developing a self-supervised machine-learning predictor for battery systems. The core of T5.1 is to design an adaptive, self-supervised CeNN predictor, which leverages a student-teacher learning architecture. This enables the model to continuously adapt its parameters in response to new operational data, providing a robust and scalable solution for real-time, data-driven battery modeling and health optimization.

T5.1 advances the project objectives by developing a suite of complementary models, each addressing a critical aspect. The task delivers:

- An adaptive, self-supervised CeNN predictor for real-time state of health (SoH) and operational parameter estimation [1, 4].
- MCO for staged constant-current (CC) charging profiles to balance speed, safety, and battery life.
- Long-term state forecasting (LTSF) models for lifecycle-aware predictive maintenance [2, 3].

All models are validated on publicly available benchmark datasets. This task directly supports:

- Fast, safe charging operations
- Accurate SoH estimation and forecasting
- Autonomous model adaptation to changing conditions
- Real-time, embedded deployment for digital twin platforms

T5.1’s approach is integrated and modular, allowing each model to be used independently or as part of a unified framework. The key methodologies and innovations are described below:

2.3 Adaptable cellular neural network predictor

The CeNN-based predictor follows a student-teacher learning architecture which allows to:

- Adapt its parameters in response to changing battery states and operational conditions [1,4].
- Deliver real-time, high-accuracy estimates of SoH, capacity, and energy.
- Low computational footprint.

The predictor is suitable for a wide range of data-driven battery modeling tasks.

2.4 Multicriteria optimization for staged charging profiles

Traditional CC-CV charging protocols do not adequately balance charging speed with safety and degradation. In T5.1, we innovate by segmenting the CC phase into adaptive stages, each optimized using MCO algorithms. This approach:

- Dynamically optimizes charging current ramp rates in each stage to rapidly reach the target voltage while controlling thermal and chemical stress.
- Allows fine-grained trade-offs between charging speed, safety, and battery longevity, all tuned in real time.
- Integrates temperature and SoH constraints directly into the optimization process, resulting in safer and more efficient charging cycles.

This method is crucial for enabling ultra-fast charging applications without sacrificing battery health or safety.

2.5 Long-term state forecasting for predictive maintenance

Long-term forecasting of battery SoH and capacity fade is essential for predictive maintenance and operational planning. The LTSF models developed in T5.1:

- Employ both frequency- and time-domain representations to accurately predict SoH trajectories over extended horizons (e.g., 48 to 720+ cycles).
- Use model architectures with significantly lower complexity than state-of-the-art transformer models, making them practical for deployment [2, 3].
- Support second-life and recycling strategies by providing reliable end-of-life predictions.

3. Results and impact

The innovations developed in T5.1 have resulted in measurable improvements across all critical dimensions of battery management. Specifically:

- **SoH prediction:** The CeNN predictor delivers real-time, accurate SoH estimates, outperforming classical approaches and providing reliability for embedded use [1, 4].
- **MCO:** Clear interfaces to modelling approaches from WP2 are implemented.

- **DoE/DoS:** The ITWM technology has been utilized for a demonstration case, including flexible strategies for enhancing the predictive power of surrogates from few to many data, demonstrated for electrolyte characterization/optimization.
- **Charging optimization:** The staged CC charging protocol with MCO achieves significantly faster charging while maintaining strict safety and health limits.
- **Lifecycle management:** LTSF models offer robust, long-term forecasts, enabling proactive and cost-effective maintenance strategies [2, 3].

Contributions to the BatCAT impacts include:

- Modelling support for increased battery performance and lifespan.
- Enhanced predictive maintenance and second-life applications.
- Support flexible, scalable digital twin deployments.
- Concrete contributions to project objectives KO5, KO6, and KO7.

4. Conclusion

The AI/ML models implemented mainly in Task T5.1 are designed to be continuously updatable, and this will be done as soon as new data are available either from the consortium or from the literature. The APIs of these models are integrated into the MCO and DoE/DoS modules from Task T5.2, so that a first demonstration of aspects of digital twins, the overarching goal of BatCAT, was successful. It is to be expected that the developments presented in this deliverable report are updated as the project evolves, since retraining of the models from Task T5.1 and numerical subtleties when it comes to the integration of more sophisticated models from WP2 into the MCO and DoE/DoS approaches will continue.

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Annex 1: Software modules for MCO and tutorial use case

Multicriteria Optimization (MCO) and model-based Design-of-Experiment/Simulation (DoE, DoS): Use Case, architecture and implementation modules

Peter Klein^{a,*}, Marco Baldan^a

^a*Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics ITWM, Fraunhofer Platz 1, D-67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany*

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*Corresponding author
Email address: peter.klein@itwm.fraunhofer.de (Peter Klein)

1. Introduction

In BatCAT, we strive for the development of a general set of software modules implementing Multi Criteria Optimization MCO and model based Design-of-Experiment/-Simulation DoE, DoS to be integrated in a general platform supporting the digital-twin approach taken by BatCAT. The purpose of this document is to introduce the mathematical background behind the methodologies used, to define an initial implementation architecture, and to present a reduced use-case which serves as a tutorial for the mathematical concepts.

This tutorial starts with a hypothetical business case inspired by a chemical engineering challenge: a toy reaction performed in an idealized batch reactor. From a modelling perspective, the batch is described using a standard approach, namely reaction kinetics differential equations describing the dynamics of substance concentrations. The specific model used here admits an analytical solution, so the forward simulation in this tutorial is fast, in contrast to many physics based models to be used in BatCAT. Then, a mapping of the toy system to a simulation workflow will get constructed. Already in this tutorial, the idea to relate business cases to use cases is put forward as well. In particular, the relation of design and objective space (KPI and cost measures of the business case) is outlined. Together with constraints describing the reactor capabilities and business requirements, a multi-criteria optimization model and a solution strategy based on existing solvers will be set up.

Implementation modules are described in a CRC like style: the responsibilities and collaborations between implementation modules will get identified and a high level description of the data attributes and functionalities of the implementation modules is suggested.

After the introduction of Multi-Criteria Optimization, this tutorial discuss the concept of optimal model based experimental design, again in a multi-criteria setting. Conceptually, optimal DoE/DoS has many similarities to MCO: the MCO design space is the DoE/DoS parameter space and the MCO objectives/KPIs relate to DoE/DoS experiment/simulation results. However, as discussed below, the focus of what is to be considered as being "optimal" is somewhat different leading to adapted numerical solution strategies.

2. The hypothetical business case used in this tutorial

The business case, we want to use in this tutorial, including a reference implementation, consists of a hypothetical reaction of two educts, A and B in a liquid:

Figure 2.1: Flowchart of the batch reactor and the up-stream purification.

where P is the product. In practical applications, no substance is pure and very often side reactions show up. We assume that only one educt, A , contains traces of some non-reactive contaminant, C , and we denote a side product by S . Thus, the above reaction scheme generalizes to

k_P, k_S are the reaction constants for product and side reactions. We assume that no other reaction occurs, thus the **side product is distinguished from the product by a lower reaction constant**.

The reaction process runs in a batch reactor with ideal temperature control and mixing and the reaction preserves the volume (no activities), see fig. 2.1. The educts from suppliers are stored in batches and the supply chain shall persist due to long standing contracts. However, an up-stream purification step for A is used in order to purify A before loading in the reactor from a buffer store of

the purification apparatus. This purification step is assumed to be, from a technological point of view, ideal and shall not be touched upon. But purification comes at a price which shall be taken into account.

The process may be stopped by a fast unloading of the reactor and no reaction takes place after unloading. The reaction constants are known to be non-linear functions of the reactor temperature, and the product reaction rate is always higher than the side product reaction rate. Thus, the purity of the product P may be maximized (KPI) by tuning the temperature. But a high temperature leads to a high cost in the temperature control of the reactor. On the other hand, the more contamination C in A is allowed, the cheaper the educt; but the non-reactive C dilutes the Product P and has thus a negative effect on the quality. We therefore face conflicting goals. In the next paragraph, we will construct a toy kinetic models for the reaction process and a reactor.

3. Kinetic reaction model: simulation workflow and data foundation

3.1. The reactor model

The batch reactor has a certain volume, V_r , and it is assumed that the loading and unloading of educts from their tanks is much faster than the reactions. The dispersion of the educts is assumed to be ideal throughout the reaction process. The temperature control of the reactor leads to an homogeneous temperature in the reaction volume. The reactor gets loaded with educt B , assumed to be ideal, and educt \tilde{A} from the purification apparatus buffer, which contains, beside educt A , a contamination by C at a known level, see figure 2.1 for details. The particle densities of all educts, ρ_X , and the molecular masses, m_X , are assumed to be known. We denote by $[X]_e$ the volume concentration of a substance X in his feed tank and treat the contaminated educt \tilde{A} as if it had been mixed with substance C . Mixing processes are controlled by a loading volume V_X for each substance. The initial mixture in the reactor is then described by mixture parameters θ_e, θ_m . In the \tilde{A} buffer tank, we have the following concentrations:

$$\begin{aligned} [A]_e &= \rho_A \cdot (1 - \theta_e) \\ [C]_e &= \rho_C \cdot \theta_e \\ \theta_e &= \frac{V_C}{V_A + V_C}. \end{aligned}$$

In the B tank, we have a pure substance at known particle density $\rho_B = [B]_e$.

For the mixture in the reactor, once again controlled by volume loading, we take into account that \tilde{A} gets loaded. This leads to the following volume concentrations in the reactor before the reaction starts:

$$\begin{aligned}
[A]_0 &= \rho_A \cdot (1 - \theta_m) \cdot (1 - \theta_e) \\
[C]_0 &= \rho_C \cdot (1 - \theta_m) \cdot \theta_e \\
[B]_0 &= \rho_B \cdot \theta_m \\
\theta_m &= \frac{V_B}{V_{\tilde{A}} + V_B} \\
[P]_0 &= [S]_0 = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

Since we neglect volume effects (activities), the initial concentrations are functions of the mixing parameters and the particle densities of the pure substances only, and product and side product are absent.

The reactor processing cost model takes into account the temperature control and the reaction time τ :

$$cost_{prod} = \tau \cdot (T - 20^\circ\text{C})^2 \cdot W, \tag{3.2}$$

W : cost per Kelvin squared and time.

The materials cost for the ideal educt B is retrieved from supplier information, the cost for educt \tilde{A} in the buffer tank takes additionally into account the purification costs:

$$cost_{mat} = V_r \cdot ((1 - \theta_m) \cdot cost_{\tilde{A}} + \theta_m \cdot cost_B), \tag{3.3}$$

$$cost_{\tilde{A}} = const_A + cost_{purification} \cdot \ln([C]_e/[C]_{supplier}).$$

$const_A$ and $cost_B$ are retrieved from pricing informations of suppliers in €/liter. $cost_{purification}$ is retrieved from the purification processing costs in the production line. It is worth mentioning that an deal purity of A comes with an infinite price. The available contamination levels in \tilde{A} and the realizable temperature range within the reaction volume are assumed to be known:

$$[C]_{min} \leq [C]_e \leq [C]_{supplier} \tag{3.4}$$

and

$$T_{min} \leq T \leq T_{max}. \quad (3.5)$$

We assume that loading and unloading, as well as labor, has negligible costs.

3.2. The kinetic reaction model, related to a simulation workflow

The kinetic model is rather simple. Denoting, as usual, the volume concentration of a substance X by $[X]$, given in *mol/liter*, the reaction kinetics is described by a system of differential equations in all components representing the **physics equation**:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[A]}{dt} &= -(k_P + k_S)[A][B] \\ \frac{d[B]}{dt} &= -(k_P + k_S)[A][B] \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} &= k_P[A][B] \\ \frac{d[S]}{dt} &= k_S[A][B] \\ \frac{d[C]}{dt} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

The reaction constants are assumed to be functions of temperature T and follow the Arrhenius law which represents a **materials relation**:

$$k = \nu e^{-\frac{\Delta H}{RT}} \quad (3.7)$$

ν : Reaction Frequency in $\frac{l}{mol \cdot s}$

ΔH : molar reaction enthalpy

R, T : Gas constant and temperature

The parameters for the materials relation

$$MR = \{\{\nu_P, \Delta H_P\}, \{\nu_S, \Delta H_S\}\} \quad (3.8)$$

are assumed to be known.

We assume that the temperature is actively controlled in the reactor, i.e. kept constant. The reaction may be stopped at a time τ by instantaneous unloading of the reactor. In this case, the kinetic reaction model (3.6) has an analytical solution at constant temperature:

$$\begin{aligned}
[A] &= [A]_0 - \alpha(t) \\
[B] &= [B]_0 - \alpha(t) \\
[P] &= [P]_0 + \frac{k_P}{k_P + k_S} \alpha(t) \\
[S] &= [S]_0 + \frac{k_S}{k_P + k_S} \alpha(t) \\
[C] &= [C]_0
\end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

with $\alpha(t)$ as an analytical function:

$$\alpha(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{[A]_0[B]_0(e^{([B]_0-[A]_0)(k_P+k_S)t}-1)}{[B]_0e^{([B]_0-[A]_0)(k_P+k_S)t}-[A]_0} & : [A]_0 \neq [B]_0 \\ [A]_0(1 - \frac{1}{[A]_0(k_P+k_S)t+1}) & : [A]_0 = [B]_0 \end{cases}$$

Since the denominator and the numerator of the branch $[A]_0 \neq [B]_0$ tend to 0 as $[A]_0$ tends to $[B]_0$, we need for numerical stability reasons another representation which explicitly handles this problem. This is accomplished by a series expansion and a factorization of the "zero by zero" division. Here, we just state the result, correct up to 10^{-9} (ppb accuracy):

$$\alpha(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{[A]_0[B]_0(e^{([B]_0-[A]_0)kt}-1)}{[B]_0e^{([B]_0-[A]_0)kt}-[A]_0} & : \epsilon \geq 0.4 \cdot 10^{-2} \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{[A]_0[B]_0 \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{([B]_0-[A]_0)^{n-1}(kt)^n}{n!}}{1+[B]_0 \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{([B]_0-[A]_0)^{n-1}(kt)^n}{n!}} + \frac{[A]_0[B]_0 \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{([A]_0-[B]_0)^{n-1}(kt)^n}{n!}}{1+[A]_0 \sum_{n=1}^4 \frac{([A]_0-[B]_0)^{n-1}(kt)^n}{n!}} \right] & : \epsilon < 0.4 \cdot 10^{-2} \end{cases} \tag{3.10}$$

$$\epsilon = |([A]_0 - [B]_0)(k_P + k_S)t|, k = k_P + k_S. \tag{3.11}$$

In the limit $[A]_0 \rightarrow [B]_0$, the second branch tends (symmetrically in $[A]_0, [B]_0$) to the analytical solution at $[A]_0 = [B]_0$.

We collocate the time dependent **physical state variable**, namely the concentrations, in one vector:

$$X^{mat} = \{[A], [B], [P], [S], [C]\}. \tag{3.12}$$

From mass conservation and by neglecting activities, we know that

$$\sum_x mass_x \cdot [X] = \rho_{mass}, \text{ constant mass density in the reactor.} \tag{3.13}$$

which, for the system (3.6), boils down to

$$[A] + [B] + 2 \cdot ([P] + [S]) + [C] = const. \tag{3.14}$$

The solution of this system needs initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_0^{mat} &= \{[A]_0, [B]_0, [P]_0, [S]_0, [C]_0\} \\
 X^{proc} &= \{T, \tau\}, \\
 X &= \{X_0^{mat}, X^{proc}\} \quad \text{as the tuneable parameters,}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.15}$$

Since the educt do not contain (traces of) the product or side product, we define a 3 dimensional vector of reactor loading concentrations:

$$X^{load} = \{[A]_0, [B]_0, [C]_0\},
 \tag{3.16}$$

whose components describe the initial loading of the reactor. These components are not independent from each other as we already noticed.

Usually, one is not only interested in one solution of systems like (3.6). Questions like 'what happens if we use a higher contamination level?' or 'can we reduce the production costs while maintaining our customers specifications?' and others show up naturally. In order to answer these questions, variations (derivatives) of the cost measures and of the concentrations after unloading of the reactor are usually employed. From a purely mathematical standpoint, we may simply differentiate the analytical solutions/approximations given in 3.10. If a numerical solution procedure is used and no analytical expression is available, as a last resort, we may use finite difference schemes. Mathematically, this is possible and used in practice. Thus, an implementation module may support 'mathematical derivatives', like the gradient operator ∇_X .

However, the physical/chemical phase space of X^{mat} is not a plain 5 dimensional real valued space. First of all, concentrations are restricted by $0 \leq [X] \leq \rho_X$, i.e. concentrations may vary between 0 and the pure substance. This may be handled in 'pure math' as well. On the other hand, it is technically not possible to modify one concentration while maintaining all the other ones; this is already reflected for instance in the mixing roles 3.1. The available phase space for the physics variables may, for instance, be represented by an obvious extension of the mixing role 3.1, leading to 4 independent mixing parameters in our case which is one dimension lower than the mathematically feasible 'space of initial concentrations' !!! Thus, physical/chemical meaningful derivatives need to be constructed according to the needs of the questions to be answered!! This will get handled below when we introduce the tutorial MCO approach.

3.3. Prototype implementation modules

The kinetic model needs to be initialized by the concentrations of the substances, the parameters of the reaction constant's model and the process parameters (reactor). This calls for the following 4 modules:

- a **ReactionKnowledgeGraph** module for the initial concentrations,
- a **MaterialsData** module for the parameters of the Arrhenius reactivities,
- a **ProcessData** module describing the process environment and its parameters,
- a **modelling workflow** module for solving the kinetics (3.6).

The information from the **ReactionKnowledgeGraph** module is rather simple: the product P may be produced by a reaction of the two educts, the pure concentrations of the substances A and B should be equal, and an estimate of the reaction time:

Module ReactionKnowledge.mod: of reaction partners.

Responsibility: Chemical inference handling based on data in a Knowledge Graph

Collaborators: The informations gathered by domain experts, patents, literature,..

Data: stores a knowledge graph

```
// return (list of) potential reaction partners for Product P. ;
1 Function (X,Y) getEducts4Product(P)
   | // look up knowledge graph, for prototype return educts A and B. ;
2   | return info (A,B);
   | // from chemical inference retrieve potential side products ;
3 Function list getSideProducts(X + Y - > Z)
   | // for prototype, return 1 element S ;
4   | return list ;
5 Function info goodPractice4Reaction(X + Y - > P)
6   | return info [A]0 == [B]0;
7 Function time estimateReactionTime(A + B - > P)
8   | return estimate;
```

The interface to the **MaterialsData** is trivial: upon request, the reaction enthalpy and the pre-factor of the Arrhenius equation are returned.

Database Materials.db: of reaction partners.

Responsibility: Stores reaction partner material parameters. Remember: only two reactions occur!!

Collaborators: Data space

Data: Information on possible reactions of A and B

```
1 Function (MassMolecule) GetComponentMolecMass(X)
   | // inspect data base ;
2   | return massX
3 Function  $\rho_X$  getPureComponentDensity(eductX)
   | // inspect data base, map (contaminated) educt name to pure substance;
4   | return  $\rho_X$ ;
5 Function  $\{\nu, \Delta H\}$  getArrheniusParams(X + Y - > Z)
   | // inspect data base;
6   | return  $\{\nu, \Delta H\}$ ;
7 Function cost getSupplierCostEduct(eductX)
   | // inspect data base;
8   | return cost ;
```

ProcessData are handled similar to the **MaterialsData**. Since the cost measures are sensitive parameters, their gradient calculation according to the tunable parameters is handled in this module as well:

Database Process.db: of reaction partners accessible to processing.

Responsibility: Accessor for processing specific parameters, i.e. the reactor.

Collaborators: Excel sheets provide basic parameters, [Materials.db](#)

Data: A reactor description, including purification info.

```
1 Function ( $cost_{prod}, \nabla_{X^{proc}} cost_{prod}$ ) calcProductionCost( $X^{proc}$ )
   | // parameters for equation (3.2) from excel sheet;
2   | return ( $cost, \nabla_{X_0} cost$ );
3 Function
   | ( $ContaminationMin, ContaminationMax$ ) getContaminationRange( $eductA$ )
   | // look up excel sheet, ContaminationMax: supplier info,
   | ContaminationMin: purification;
4   | return available contamination range;
5 Function ( $TMin, TMax$ ) getTempRange()
   | // look up excel sheet;
6   | return available temperature range;
7 Function ( $cost, \nabla_{X^{load}}$ ) calcMatCost( $X^{load}$ )
   | // supplier costs from Materials.db and use equ. (3.3);
8   | return ( $cost, \nabla_{X^{load}}$ );
9 Function reactorvolume getReactorVol()
   | // look up excel sheet;
10  | return volume of reactor;
```

The information necessary for the initialization of the kinetic model is now spread over [Materials.db](#), [Process.db](#) and [ReactionKnowledge.mod](#). We collocate these information in an Initializer module:

Module Initializer.mod: for kinetic model.

Responsibility: Initializer Strategy for the simulation of reaction kinetics

Collaborators: [Materials.db](#), [Process.db](#), [ReactionKnowledge.mod](#)

Data: Handle's to collaborators, for example supplier data bases

```

1 Function  $X_0$  getInitDataKinModel( $A + B \rightarrow P$ )
   |
   | // use midpoint for ranges ( $TMin, TMax$ ) = Process.db :: getTempRange() ;
2   |  $X :: T = 0.5 \cdot (TMin + TMax)$  ;
3   | ( $ContaminationMin, ContaminationMax$ )
4   |           = Process.db :: getContaminationRange( $A$ ) ;
5   |  $[\bar{C}] = 0.5 \cdot (ContaminationMin + ContaminationMax)$ ;
   | // Product and side product not loaded ;
6   |  $X :: [P] = X :: [S] = 0$  ;
   | //  $[A] == [B]$ , use mass conservation (3.14) ;
7   | info = ReactionKnowledge.mod :: goodPractice4Reaction( $A + B \rightarrow P$ ) ;
8   |  $E = \frac{1 - [\bar{C}]/\rho_C}{\rho_A^{-1} + \rho_B^{-1} - [\bar{C}]/(\rho_B \rho_C)}$  ;
9   | info -> ( $X :: [A] = X :: [B] = E$ ) ;
10  |  $X :: [C] = [\bar{C}](1 - \frac{X :: [B]}{\rho_B})$ 
   | // reaction time from chemical inference ;
11  |  $X :: \tau =$  ReactionKnowledge.mod :: estimateReactionTime4Reaction( $A + B \rightarrow P$ ) ;
12  | return X;

13 Function  $M$  getMaterialRelationData( $A + B \rightarrow P$ )
   |
14  |  $S =$  ReactionKnowledge.mod :: getSideProducts( $A + B \rightarrow P$ ) :: listentry ;
15  |  $M :: \{\nu_P, \Delta H_P\} =$  Materials.db :: getArrheniusParams( $A + B \rightarrow P$ ) ;
16  |  $M :: \{\nu_S, \Delta H_S\} =$  Materials.db :: getArrheniusParams( $A + B \rightarrow S$ ) ;
17  | return M;

```

Now, the Simulation workflow has only one dependency to [Initializer.mod](#). At constant temperature, the kinetic model has an analytical solution. The prototype **SimWorkflow** module implements the analytical solutions in order to return the physical state variable associated with the solution of the kinetic model. As already noted in the introduction, analytical solutions are in

general not available for most real world problems; however, the interface to numerical solutions of forward simulations is similar to the one described in the **SimWorkflow** module.

Beside the physical state variable (3.12) the gradient in the space of tunable parameters (3.15) is calculated.

Remark:

This module may act as a persistence layer for simulations already performed (another software design option could be the introduction of an additional data base). The idea is that once the simulation of a materials model takes considerable computing resources, then results might be cached and reused (including interpolations if appropriate), thus saving a lot of computing time.

Module ReactionKinetics.mod: simulates reaction kinetics.

Responsibility: Simulation of reaction kinetics

Collaborators: [Initializer.mod](#)

Data: Persistency layer for storage of simulations already performed.

```

1 Function ( $X^{mat}, \nabla_{X_0} X^{mat}$ ) runDefault( $A + B \rightarrow P$ )
   | // Use Initializer.mod and run the simulation;
2   |  $X = \text{Initializer.mod} :: \text{getInitDataKinModel}(A + B \rightarrow P)$ ;
3   |  $M = \text{Initializer.mod} :: \text{getMaterialRelationData}(A + B \rightarrow P)$ ;
4   | return self :: run( $X, M$ );
5 Function ( $X^{mat}, \nabla_{X_0} X^{mat}$ ) run( $X_0, M$ )
6   | if ( $X_0, M$ ) simulation cached then
7   |   | return cached result;
8   | else
9   |   | // implement solver of kinetic model (3.6);
10  |   | calculate reactivity constants according to Arrhenius equation (3.7)
11  |   | calculate  $X^{mat}(X :: X_{proc} :: \tau)$  according to (3.10);
12  |   | calculate  $\nabla_{X_0} X^{mat}$  ;
13  |   | cache  $\{\{X_0, M\}, \{X^{mat}, \nabla_{X_0} X^{mat}\}\}$  ;
14  |   | return ( $X^{mat}, \nabla_X X^{mat}$ ) ;
end

```

4. Multi criteria optimization

4.1. Introduction to MCO for continuous problems

In general, an MCO model has three ingredients:

- An objective space O . Each component of a vector from O represents one criterion to be optimized. By mathematical convention, we always seek for their minimization (by changing sign on criteria to be maximized).
- A design space D spanning the parameter space mapped to objectives.
- A set of constraints acting in the design space and/or in the objective space, usually given as equalities and inequalities (both linear and non-linear)

The design variables associated with the MCO problem in the batch reactor example are continuous and the objectives are differentiable. Furthermore, the objectives in the batch reactor example are functions of control variables (reaction time, temperature) and of a dynamical state variable. Thus, we deal with a multi-objective control problem. In general, these type of problems are formulated mathematically as

$$\min_{y \in D} \{O_1(X(y), y), \dots, O_n(X(y), y)\} \quad (4.1)$$

subject to

$\{c_i(y) = 0\}$: design space equality constraints

$\{C_i(y) \leq 0\}$: design space in-equality constraints

$\{g_i(O) = 0\}$: objective space equality constraints

$\{G_i(O) \leq 0\}$: objective space in-equality constraints

$\{F_i(t, X, \dot{X}) = 0\}$: state constraints, implicit rep. of ODE/PDE

The notation *min* is commonly used here as a short hand for Pareto optimality. Since usually the objectives represent conflicting goals, they may not be minimized simultaneously and we seek for best possible compromises, which in general are not unique.

Most solvers of MCO problems of this type, so called gradient based solvers, use a common strategy:

- scalarization: use a scalar product of a weight vector with the vector of objectives, thus mapping the MCO to a single criterion optimization problem.
- solve the single criterion control problem using non-linear programming (see [1] for details), the theory behind single criteria optimization problems resides on the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker theorems, see [2]:
 - solve ODE for a given design space point.
 - calculate objectives and derivatives.
 - advice new candidate design space point.
 - stop once the KKT conditions are fulfilled.

This leads to one candidate Pareto point (usually locally Pareto).

- use a strategy to modify the weight vector in order to find the next candidate Pareto point.
- If the MCO problem is not globally convex, we need to apply a filter mechanism in order to get rid of dominated points not on the global Pareto front.
- once a good enough approximation of the Pareto front is obtained: stop.

An impression on how to classify MCO problems according to the nature of the objectives and of the constraints can be found in the wikipedia articles cited above. Even within one class of MCO problems, the choice of the weight strategy and of the KKT-solver is not unique and needs to get adapted to the specific MCO problem.

4.2. *Design space, constraints and objectives for the batch reactor MCO problem*

The model ingredients will now get constructed for the business case; in the language of the EMMC, this construction is a **translation process**.

It is obvious that here we have some freedom in constructing an MCO model. For instance, we may use as design space the space of variables closely connected to the mathematical formulation given as tunable parameters, equation (3.15), subject to mass conservation (3.14) and mixing role constraints (3.1). This modelling would serve the needs of an engineer interested in 'understanding'. In this prototype, we take a somewhat different point of view: the design space shall closely reflect the tunable parameters of the process. We use as design space the process parameters and describe

the mixing process by appropriate volume fractions. We thus have a 4 dimensional design space with obvious constraints:

$$D = \{(V_{\bar{A}}, [C]_e, T, \tau) \mid 0 \leq V_{\bar{A}} \leq V_r, [C]_{min} \leq [C]_e \leq [C]_{max}, T_{min} \leq T \leq T_{max}, 0 \leq \tau\} \quad (4.2)$$

The volume load related to substance B is then given by $V_r = V_{\bar{A}} + V_B$. The initial concentrations, as functions of the design variables, now read:

$$\begin{aligned} [A]_0 &= [A]_e \cdot \frac{V_{\bar{A}}}{V_r} = \rho_A \cdot \left(1 - \frac{[C]_e}{\rho_C}\right) \cdot \frac{V_{\bar{A}}}{V_r} \\ [B]_0 &= \rho_B \cdot \frac{V_r - V_{\bar{A}}}{V_r} \\ [P]_0 &= 0 \\ [S]_0 &= 0 \\ [C]_0 &= [C]_e \cdot \frac{V_{\bar{A}}}{V_r} \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

This modelling of the design space closely reflects the needs of an operator running the reactor since the volumes to be loaded from the purification buffer and from tank B are readily retrieved from design space variables.

Now, we construct the mapping from the design space to the objective space. In natural language we have 3 objectives:

- maximize the product P, which is equivalent to a minimization of product impurities $[I]$.
- minimize the production cost $cost_{prod}$.
- minimize the materials cost $cost_{mat}$.

The product impurity is naturally modelled as a function of the physical state variables at the unloading time and implicitly as a function of temperature (via the reaction constants):

$$[I] = [S] + [C]_0 + res([A]) + res([B]) \quad (4.4)$$

$res(X)$: residual concentrations of X=A,B at final reaction time,

We collocate the KPI (4.4) and the cost measures, equations (3.2) and (3.3), in one 3 dimensional vector \tilde{O} . The mapping of the design space to these vector of objectives uses the analytical expressions obtained above, re-written as functions of the design variables in $y \in D$. For the physical

state variable X^{mat} , this is done by using the initial conditions (4.3) and the reaction constants, as functions of temperature T , from the Arrhenius equation (3.7). Similar algebraic manipulations of the mixing parameters lead to cost measures as function of variables from the design space. Thus, the 3 objectives are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{O}_1 &= [I](X(y)) \\ \tilde{O}_2 &= cost_{prod}(X(y)) \\ \tilde{O}_3 &= cost_{mat}(X(y))\end{aligned}$$

and derivatives are readily constructed analytically using the chain rule based on the analytical solution for the time depended state variable given in equation (3.10). Since the residual impurities and the corresponding directional derivatives are assumed to be very small at long enough reaction times, we use a numerically more stable variant of the objectives:

$$\begin{aligned}O_1 &= \ln([I](X(y))/[C]_0) \\ O_2 &= cost_{prod}(X(y)) \\ O_3 &= cost_{mat}(X(y)).\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

Thus, the KPI from equation 4.4 is redefined by it's logarithm.

The MCO problem, formulated as a control problem, now reads:

$$\min_y \{O_1(X(y)), \dots, O_3(X(y))\}$$

subject to

$$y : T \leq T_{max} \text{ from (3.5)}$$

$$y : T \geq T_{min}$$

$$y : [C]_e \leq [C]_{max} \text{ from (3.4)}$$

$$y : [C]_e \geq [C]_{min}$$

ODE(3.6) with materials relation and initial conditions as functions of y

$$\tau \leq \tau_{max}$$

We restrict the reaction time by a τ_{max} for computational reasons: the contamination of the final product may be minimized at infinite reaction time only, which for a simulator means infinite computing time (similar to convergence criteria of linear algebra solvers). We see, that up to the ODE constraint, all constraints are linear in-equalities. (*Note: if we use the 'mathematical' formulation discussed above, then the constraints need to reflect the mixing roles as a non-linear equality.*)

The formulation as a control problem, however, has some technical difficulties related to the MCO solver implementations to be used in the prototype, namely that the MCO solver implementations 'want' to solve the ODE internally using their own solver and estimates the gradient informations. In a more general situation we use a modelling workflow and this needs to get integrated in a deep manner into the MCO solvers (too much for a prototype!!). Since we have an analytical solution at hand, we use in this prototype another MCO modelling which uses these analytical solutions and thus turning the control problem to a standard MCO problem.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_y \{O_1(X(y)), \dots, O_3(X(y))\} \\
 & \text{subject to} \\
 & y : T \leq T_{max} \text{ from (3.5)} \\
 & y : T \geq T_{min} \tag{4.6} \\
 & y : [C]_e \leq [C]_{max} \text{ from (3.4)} \\
 & y : [C]_e \geq [C]_{min} \\
 & y : \tau \leq \tau_{max}
 \end{aligned}$$

the functions $X(y)$ are then the solutions (3.10) of the kinetic model (3.6) with initial conditions (4.3).

5. MCO implementation modules

5.1. MCO solver and associated wrappers for MCO problem set-up

The description of the implementation modules used in the prototype implementation of the batch reactor example starts from the central result: a point-wise approximation of the Pareto front.

Database ParetoProcess.db: represents the solution of the BDSS system

Responsibility: Handles a point-wise representation of the Pareto surface and -front.

```
// return the current representation of the Pareto solution.;  
1 getParetoPointContainer( $A + B - > P$ ) ;  
   // input is a Pareto optimal desing point and corresponding objectives;  
2 insert( $\{ y , O(y) \}$ ) ;
```

One interface will be used by the MCO module, the other one by a tool which allows to explore the Pareto surface.

In this tutorial implementation one interface wrapper around existing MCO solver implementations is used. This approach makes the MCO solver exchangeable. While analyzing a couple of MCO solver implementations, a common style for interacting with design spaces, objectives and constraints can be identified. This allows for a wrapper design in tandem of 4 wrappers around design space, objectives, constraints and MCO solvers. First, we describe the MCO wrapper which internally calls all the other wrappers, and extract from there the interfaces to the three other wrapper modules.

Module MCOwrapper.mod: solves the MCO problem.

Responsibility: Wrapper interface to existing MCO solvers

Collaborators: uses internally an MCO solver implementation MCOimpl,

[Initializer.mod](#), [Objectives.mod](#), [Constraints.mod](#), and [ParetoProcess.db](#)

```
// Initialization ;
1 Function Init ( MCOsetup objects: Objectives and Constraints )
    | // Init() is specific to the MCOimpl used!! ;
2 | convert MCOsetup to MCO setup in MCOimpl;
    | // Basic MCO Loop in MCOimpl, included for clarity here !!! ;
3 Function MCOimpl : solve()
4 | while Pareto solutions not dense enough do
    | | // Scalarization: uses a strategy implemented in i.e. ACADO or
    | | DAKOTA ;
5 | | weight3 = MCOimpl : ScalStrat : getWeights() ;
    | | // construct new objective function evaluation procedure ;
6 | | newObjective = weight3 · MCOimpl : objectiveInterface();
    | | // Solve scalar problem, inner loop, KKT solver 'knows' constraints ;
7 | | MCOimpl : KKTsolver(newObjective);
    | | // store Pareto optimal result ;
8 | | MCOimpl : storeCurrentResult();
9 | end
    | // KKT solver in MCOimpl, included for clarity here !!! ;
10 Function MCOimpl : KKTsolver(singeObjectiveCalc)
11 | y = MCOimpl : InitValueDesignSpace();
12 | while KKT optimality conditions not reached do
13 | | objVal = singleObjectiveCalc(y); gradobj = ∇yofsingleobjective; suggest new y
    | | based on gradobj (line search for instance) ;
14 | end
15 Function solve()
16 | MCOimpl : solve();
17 | ParetoProcess.db = ParetoFilter(MCOimpl : results). ;
```

In the implementation of the tutorial batch reactor case, we use a standard python package which contains a KKT solver and hand-craft a scalarization strategy by using a Gibbs triangle approach for the weights, a construction well known by chemists. As a remark: many other scalarization strategies are used in real world problems, they are usually adapted to the problem at hand in particular when the evaluation of the objectives is time consuming.

5.2. Design space-, objective-, and constraints-wrapper for the prototype

From the MCO module description, [MCOwrapper.mod](#), we know that a MCOsetup is necessary for the MCO solver wrapper. Obviously, the MCOsetup is closely connected to a general MCO problem described in (4.1). We start with a KPI wrapper

Module KPI.mod: for reaction kinetics.

Responsibility: Calculates the KPI's and mathematical gradients

Collaborators: [ReactionKinetics.mod](#), [Initializer.mod](#)

Data: Stores materials realtion data M by accessing the [Initializer.mod](#)

// Prototype implementation: $\ln([I]/[C]_0)$ and derivatives ;

```

1 Function ( $KPI, \nabla_X KPI$ ) evalKPI( $X$ )
2   ( $X^{mat}, \nabla_X X^{mat}$ ) = ReactionKinetics.mod :: run( $X, M$ ) ;
3   calculate  $[I]$  by equation (4.4) ;
4   calculate  $\nabla_X [I]$  by using  $\nabla_X X^{mat}$  and the chain rule ;
5   calculate objective by equation (4.5),  $O_1$  and it's derivative ;
6   return ( $\ln([I]/[C]_0), \nabla_X \dots$ );

```

In this module, for flexibility reasons, we use the math gradient. As we have seen above, the construction of an MCO problem is not straight forward and needs to get adapted to the persona using the final BDSS system.

The KPI and the cost measures are collocated in the objective module. We use here directly the design space of the prototype MCO system given in (4.6) at the interface, which is simply an array of dimension 4:

Module Objectives.mod: used in prototype

Responsibility: calculates objectives and their gradients in the design space

Collaborators: [KPI.mod](#), [Process.db](#), [Materials.db](#)

```
1 Function  $(O, \nabla_y O) \text{objCalc}(y \in D, (4.2))$ 
2    $Xmat = \text{transform}(y)$  by equation (4.3) using Materials.db ;
3    $X = \{Xmat, y :: T, y :: \tau\}$  ;
4    $(O[0], \nabla_X O[0]) = \text{KPI.mod} :: \text{evalKPI}(X)$  ;
5    $X^{proc} = \{y :: T, y :: \tau\}$  ;
6    $(O[1], \nabla_{X^{proc}} O[1]) = \text{Process.db} :: \text{calcProdCost}(X^{proc})$  ;
7    $(O[1], \nabla_X O[1]) = (O[1], \nabla_{X^{proc}} O[1])$  augmented by "0" for  $X_0^{mat}$  Variables;
8    $X^{load} = \{Xmat :: [A], Xmat :: [C], Xmat :: [B]\}$  ;
9    $(O[2], \nabla_{X^{load}} O[2]) = \text{Process.db} :: \text{calcMatCost}(X^{load})$  ;
10   $(O[2], \nabla_X O[2]) = (O[2], \nabla_{X^{load}} O[2])$  augmented by "0" ;
11   $(O[2], \nabla_y O[2])$  calculated from  $(O[2], \nabla_X O[2])$  and the chain rule ;
12  return $(O, \nabla_y O)$ 
```

All constraints are handled in a constraints module. In the prototype MCO (4.6), we use linear constraints in each individual dimension of the design space. (*However, much more general constraints are possible, see (4.1)*). A special role is played by the constraint on the reaction time: this constraint is for numerical stability/feasibility reasons and thus needs to be specified by a Translator with the help of the [ReactionKnowledge.mod](#).

Module Constraints.mod: for reaction kinetics.

Responsibility: handles the linear constraints of the prototype MCO (4.6)

Collaborators: [Process.db](#), [ReactionKnowledge.mod](#)

```
1 Function rangeInfo getLinearConstraints(DesignSpaceDim)
   | // assumes a 0 based counting;
2 Function
   (ContaminationMin, ContaminationMax) getContaminationRange(eductA)
   | // look up data space;
3 | return available contamination range;
4 Function (TMin, TMax) getTempRange()
   | // look up data space;
5 | return available temperature range;
   // Numerical feasibility ;
6 Function  $\tau_{max}$  maxReactionTime()
7 |  $\tau =$  ReactionKnowledge.mod :: estimateReactionTime4Reaction(A + B  $\rightarrow$  P) ;
   | // Translators guess;
8 |  $\tau = \tau \cdot 10$  ;
9 | return  $\tau$ ;
```

The main driver for the prototype is now rather short:

Procedure *Main* Returns the decision vector D and the objective vector O of a Pareto optimal solution.

```
1 Function Main()
2 | { MCO description } ;
3 | Constraints.mod::init() ;
4 | Objectives.mod::init() ;
5 | MCOwrapper.mod::init() ;
6 | MCOwrapper.mod::solve() ;
```

5.3. Approximation of the Pareto front and cognitive surrogates

Using cognitive tools, the [ParetoProcess.db](#) will be extended towards continuous interpolation between its entries. The model obtained this way will be used in a real time explorer of Pareto optimal

Figure 5.1: Mocup of an interactive Pareto surface and - front explorer.

product and production schemes. This explorer may be implemented similar to the mocup presented already in figure 5.1, but the extension towards continuous interpolation and navigation is not part of the source code accompanying the tutorial.

An implementation of such an interactive Pareto front browser is readily available, based on an Excel sheet containing the Pareto front in its columns, without continuous interpolation/navigation capabilities.

6. Optimal experimental design

6.1. *Introduction to optimal design of experiment/simulation for continuous problems*

ToDo: include the basic ideas behind DoE/DoS.

7. Acknowledgement

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8. References

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